

The Schrödinger Equation as a Lagrangian Mechanics Solution to the Solar System and the Atom's Proton

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List of Constants, Variables, And Data In This Paper

$$m_p : 1.67262E - 27k g \text{ (Proton Mass)}$$

$$r_p : 0.833E - 15m \text{ (Proton Radius)}$$

$$h : 6.62607E - 34J \cdot s \text{ (Planck Constant)}$$

$$c : 299,792,458m /s \text{ (Light Speed)}$$

$$G : 6.67408E - 11N \frac{m^2}{s^2} \text{ (Gravitational Constant)}$$

$$\alpha : 1/137 \text{ (Fine Structure Constant)}$$

$$q_p : 1.6022E - 19C \text{ (Proton Charge)}$$

$$q_e : 1.6022E - 19C \text{ (Electron Charge)}$$

$$k_e : 8.988E9 \frac{Nm^2}{C^2} \text{ (Coulomb Constant)}$$

$$\hbar_{\odot} : 2.8314E33J \cdot s \text{ (The Author's Solar System Planck-Constant)}$$

$$M_e : 5.972E24kg \text{ (Earth Mass)}$$

$$R_e : 6.378E6m \text{ (Earth Radius)}$$

$$M_m : 7.34767309E22kg \text{ (Moon Mass)}$$

$$R_m : 1.7374E6m \text{ (Moon Radius)}$$

$$M_{\odot} : 1.989E30kg \text{ (Mass of Sun)}$$

$$R_{\odot} : 6.96E8m \text{ (Sun Radius)}$$

$$r_e : 1.496E11m = 1AU \text{ (Earth Orbital Radius)}$$

$$r_m : 3.844E8m \text{ (Moon Orbital Radius)}$$

Earth day=(24)(60)(60)=86,400 seconds. Using the Moon's orbital velocity at aphelion, and Earth's orbital velocity at perihelion we have:

$$KE_m = \frac{1}{2}(7.347673E22kg)(966m/s)^2 = 3.428E28J \text{ (Kinetic Energy Moon)}$$

$$KE_e = \frac{1}{2}(5.972E24kg)(30,290m/s)^2 = 2.7396E33J \text{ (Kinetic Energy Earth)}$$

Introduction One can speak of the structure of the long term structure of the solar system. The whole object of developing a theory for the way planetary systems form is that they meet the following criterion: They predict the Titius-Bode rule for the distribution of the planets; the distribution gives the planetary orbital periods from Newton's Universal Law of Gravitation. The distribution of the planets is chiefly predicted by three factors: The inward forces of gravity from the parent star, the outward pressure gradient from the stellar production of radiation, and the outward inertial forces as a cloud collapses into a flat disc around the central star. These forces separate the flat disc into rings, agglomerations of material, each ring from which a different planet forms at its central distance from the star (they have widths). In a theory of planetary formation from a primordial disc, it should predict the Titius-Bode rule for the distribution of planets today, which was the distribution of the rings from which the planets formed.

Also, the Earth has been in the habitable zone since 4 billion years ago when it was at 0.9 AU. Today it is at 1AU, and that habitable zone can continue to 1.2 AU. So we can speak of the distance to the Earth over much time. The Earth and Sun formed about 4.6 billion years ago. As the Sun very slowly loses mass over millions of years as it burns fuel doing fusion, the Earth slips microscopically further out in its orbit over long periods of time. The Earth orbit increases by about 0.015 meters per year. The Sun only loses 0.00007% of its mass annually. The Earth is at 1AU=1.496E11m. We have $0.015\text{m}/1.496\text{E}11\text{m}/\text{AU}=1.00267\text{E}-13\text{AU}$. So,

$$(1.00267\text{E} - 13\text{AU}/\text{year})(1\text{E}9\text{years}) = 0.0001\text{AU}$$

The Earth will only move out one ten thousandth of an AU in a billion years. Anatomically modern humans have only been around for about three hundred thousand years. Civilization began only about six thousand years ago.

The unit of a second becomes important in my theory. We got the second from the rotation period of the Earth at the time the moon came to perfectly eclipse the Sun. The Moon slows the Earth rotation and this in turn expands the Moon's orbit, so it is getting larger as the Earth loses energy to the Moon. The Earth day gets longer by 0.0067 hours per million years, and the Moon's orbit gets 3.78 cm larger per year.

That is as the Earth's day gets longer and the lunar orbit grows larger, we got the second at the time that the Earth day was what it is during the epoch when the Moon perfectly eclipses the Sun, 24 hours.

The near perfect eclipse is a mystery in the sense that it came to happen when anatomically modern humans arrived on the scene, even before that, perhaps around Homo Erectus and the beginning of the Stone Age. The Earth day was 18 hours long, long before that, 1.4 billion years ago. Homo Erectus is around two to three million years ago. In our theory, we suggest conditions for life may be optimized when the earth day is about 24 hours long, what it is today, because the earth day of 24 hours has a characteristic time of 1 second in our theory to be presented.

Abstract

In quantum mechanics the wave function squared is a probability density where in classical mechanics the density of the protoplanetary disc that gave rise to our Solar System is a classical quantity. Planets are classical objects with masses and their deBroglie wavelengths are absurdly small, making quantum effects negligible. Yet, I have a solution that works very well that is analogous to quantum solutions to the wave equation at every turn. The reason why is that several interesting assumptions are made that turn treating the surface density of the protoplanetary disc from which the planets formed as a classical field analogous to the probability density. As such we find reiteration of self-similar elements on the microscale (protons) to the macroscale (Solar System) and up to Cosmological aspects of the Universe, like the Big Bang. It is deeply interesting because the assumptions that make everything work have deep implications. Such assumptions would be that the conditions for the Moon perfectly eclipsing the Sun as seen from the Earth are part of the solution to a star system with an optimally habitable planet. That they are part of the Earth's functional structure. As well as the Earth's moon in size and mass is the scaling factor for the Earth's orbit around the Sun, giving the Sun a size of 400 and yielding a base unit of time, a characteristic time for Solar System mechanics of 1 second. This has archaeological implications because the second comes ultimately from the Ancient Sumerians, who first settled down from wandering and gathering to invent writing, mathematics, and agriculture, and from the rotation period of the Earth which determines its day. We will see here that the second is also a characteristic time for the proton, and we use it to construct a theory for its inertia, its quality to push back when pushed on, giving it its mass. We will see that a Planck-type constant for the Solar System is given by the kinetic energy of the Earth, the third planet orbiting the Sun which is in the Goldilock's zone for habitability allowing for water to exist in all three of its phases. We further find that the kinetic energy of the Moon tempered by the kinetic energy of the Earth gives a characteristic time of one second for the Earth's current 24 hour day.

A Brief Historical Overview of how this Theory Formed

It all started when I was trying to work out a theory for inertia, that property of matter to resist change in motion: when you push on it, it pushes back. The more of it there is, the more it pushes back. I had decided to start with the constants, like the gravitational constant, because I figured they measured the properties of space and time. I eventually wrote an expression that to my surprise was equal to 1 second:

$$\left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{Gc}} \right) \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} = 1second$$

I found that interesting and figured if the proton was characterized by the second, and the second came from the ancient Sumerians dividing-up the rotation period of the Earth into 24 hours, each hour into 60 minutes, and each minute into 60 seconds from their base 12 and base 60 mathematics, that it had to have something to do with the celestial motions and periods they observed in the sky, that if the second was natural, then it would be in the motions of the Earth, Moon, Sun, and stars. My first guess, which panned out was that the kinetic energy of the Moon to the kinetic energy of the Earth times the 24 hour day, should be one second, or close to it. At first I found it was close to it, but then I made an adjustment for the Earth's tilt to its orbit of $\theta = 23.5^\circ$ and it came out exact for all practical purposes. I got

$$\frac{KE_m}{KE_e}(EarthDay)\cos(\theta) = 1.0seconds$$

I then thought this was quantum mechanical and that I should make a Planck-type constant for the Solar System. I found it was in this very equation because it is in joule-seconds which could be the kinetic energy of the earth times one second in the above equation, so I had:

$$\hbar_{\odot} = (1second)KE_e$$

I then thought I don't need to solve the Schrodinger Wave equation of quantum mechanics for the Solar System, but just look at the equation of Niels Bohr for the Bohr model of the atom, which he wrote down before the Schrodinger equation existed from suggesting the proton had discrete orbitals for the electrons and was quantized by \hbar , the Planck constant, he didn't know why or how it quantized like this by integer multiples of \hbar , but he found it worked. He was inspired to do this by the emission spectra of hydrogen for different energies, he suggested after the electron jumped from one orbital to another by adding energy, that when it fell back in it would emit light of a particular frequency. So I looked at his equation for the energies of orbitals E_n and their orbital distances r_n :

$$E_n = - \frac{Z^2(k_e e^2)^2 m_e}{2\hbar^2 n^2}$$

$$r_n = \frac{n^2 \hbar^2}{Z k_e e^2 m_e}$$

It later turned out for the hydrogen atom the case of $Z=1$ (1 proton) that the Schrodinger equation had these as the solutions. That equation in spherical coordinates is:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} \right] \psi + V(r)\psi = E\psi$$

This equation can be solved for the hydrogen atom giving the results of the the Bohr equations, but that is for $Z=1$, for other elements, like $Z=2,3,4\dots$ The equation becomes to difficult to solve. But Bohr's equation works for these other values of Z .

I then looked at Bohr's equations and changed the Coulomb constant k_e to the gravitational constant G , which changed charge e into mass m , put in my Planck-type constant for the Solar System, \hbar_{\odot} , did the dimensional analysis and wrote:

$$KE_e = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

$$r_n = \frac{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$$

They worked correctly to better than 99% for the Earth/Moon/Sun system, which was the $n=3$ orbit. I knew I couldn't use Z , which would ridiculously be the number of protons in the Sun, so since this was gravity, I used the radius of the Sun, R_{\odot} . But, since the Moon of the Earth was mysteriously appearing in my equations, I used it to normalize the radius of the Sun, which gave it a radius of 400 (400 moon radii). This made it work. I then realized since we were dealing with the Earth, the most optimally suited for life planet in the Solar System, and thought since this was because the Moon optimizes the conditions for life on Earth by holding the Earth at its inclination to its orbit around the Sun allowing for the season's and preventing temperature extremes, that the Earth perfectly eclipsing the Sun as seen from the Earth had meaning, and I wrote the the conditions for a perfect eclipse, which are the radius of the Sun to the radius of the Moon equals the orbital radius of the Earth to the orbital radius of the Moon. I then thought this might be a condition for habitable planets to be optimally successful and wrote it:

$$\frac{r_{planet}}{r_{moon}} = \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}}$$

Later I used this in my solutions for habitable star systems by spectral type of the stars. Finally, I wanted to formulate the ground state for the solar system and used the equation from the Bohr atom, which is

$$r_1 = \frac{\hbar^2}{ke^2 m_e}$$

$$r_1 \approx 0.529E - 10m$$

Thus writing it with the mass of the Moon

$$\frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} = \frac{(2.8314E33)^2}{(6.67408E - 11)(7.34763E22kg)^3} = 3.0281E8m$$

Noticing this in meters, is about the speed of light in meters per second, if I multiplied by one over c , the speed of light, it would be 1 second:

$$\frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{1}{c} = 1second$$

It was at this point that I was sure I was onto something. Later, playing with the equations, I ended up with another equation for a second using the proton. It was

$$\left(\sqrt{\phi \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = 1second$$

Where ϕ is the golden ratio (0.618). Equating the left of this with left of my first equation the got the ball rolling

$$\left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} \right) \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} = 1second$$

I found it yielded the radius of the proton as

$$r_p = \phi \cdot \frac{h}{c m_p}$$

It was at this point that I realized I had the rudiments for a kind of theory of everything that bridged the microcosms to the macrocosmos. This theory will be addressed more completely in this paper, including putting forth a theory for the mass of a proton, and applying it to stars of other spectral types (masses, sizes, colors, and temperatures) for formulating how other stars might structure the mechanics of their habitable planets.

A Classical Field For The Schrodinger Equation

(This section done in collaboration with Deep Seek) To have not a Schrodinger wave equation for the Solar System, but a Schrodinger-like Lagrangian classical field equation for the protoplanetary disc from which the planets arose, we begin with the potentials. We have

Gravitational potential

$$V_{grav} = -\frac{GM_{\odot}}{r}$$

Centrifugal potential from the disc rotation

$$V_{cent} = -\frac{L^2}{2r^2}$$

Where $L = mr^2\Omega$ is the specific angular momentum, and $\Omega = \sqrt{GM_{\odot}/r^3}$ is the Keplerian angular velocity. Substituting L :

$$V_{cent} = -\frac{GM_{\odot}}{2r}$$

Pressure term (from gas dynamics):

$$\mathcal{P} = \frac{\delta P}{\delta \Sigma} c_s^2 \ln \Sigma$$

\mathcal{P} is the specific pressure term, it divides pressure of the disc by density giving units of potential per mass so it can be added to potential V . c_s is the speed of sound in the protoplanetary disc. The total potential is

$$V_{eff} = V_{grav} + V_{cent} + P = -\frac{3GM_{\odot}}{2r} + \mathcal{P}$$

The Lagrangian density is:

$$\mathcal{L} = i\hbar_{\odot}\Psi^*\partial\Psi - \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{2\Sigma_0} |\nabla\Psi|^2 - \left(-\frac{3GM_{\odot}}{2r} + \mathcal{P}\right) |\Psi|^2$$

Where $\Psi = \sqrt{\Sigma}e^{i\phi}$, the so-called Madelung transform and Σ_0 is the reference surface density of the protoplanetary disc. Thus the Euler-Lagrange equation, where we see that the Schrodinger wave equation can be seen as a classical field, is varying \mathcal{L} with respect to Ψ^*

$$i\hbar_{\odot}\partial_t\Psi = -\frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{2\Sigma_0}\nabla^2\Psi + \left(\frac{-3GM_{\odot}}{2r} + \mathcal{P}\right)\Psi$$

And, we have the Schrodinger-like equation is:

$$i\hbar_{\odot}\partial_t\Psi = -\frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{2}\Sigma_0\nabla^2\Psi + V_{eff}\Psi$$

Now we write out the full hydrodynamic equations..

For a thin, rotating protoplanetary disc we have the continuity equation which is the conservation of mass in flows, that going into a system equals that going out:

$$\partial_t\Sigma + \nabla \cdot (\Sigma\vec{v}) = 0$$

Momentum Equation

$$\partial_t\vec{v} + (\vec{v} \cdot \nabla)\vec{v} = -\frac{\nabla P}{\Sigma} - \nabla\Phi + \Omega^2 r\hat{r}$$

The third term on the right is the centrifugal term. $\Phi = \frac{GM_{\odot}}{r}$ is the gravitational potential.

$\Omega = \sqrt{GM_{\odot}/r^3}$ is the Keplerian angular velocity, and P is the gas pressure. Now we consider the Madelung transformation with the centrifugal potential. Express the surface density Σ and velocity \vec{v} via a complex field $\Psi = \sqrt{\Sigma}e^{i\phi}$.

Velocity Potential: $\vec{v} = \nabla\phi$ is the irrotational flow.

$$\text{Continuity Equation: } \partial_t |\Psi|^2 + \nabla \cdot (|\Psi|^2 \nabla\phi) = 0$$

The continuity equation is conservation of mass, the mass flowing into a system equals that leaving.

$$\text{The Bernoulli Equation. } \partial_t\phi + \frac{1}{2} |\nabla\phi|^2 + \frac{GM_{\odot}}{r} - \frac{1}{2}\Omega^2 r^2 + \frac{\delta\mathcal{P}}{\delta\Sigma} = 0$$

The Bernoulli equation states for a steady flow the sum of pressure, kinetic energy per unit volume and potential energy per unit volume remains constant.

The centrifugal potential $-\frac{1}{2}\Omega^2 r^2 = -\frac{GM_{\odot}}{2r}$ cancels half the gravitational term leaving

$$\partial_t\phi + \frac{1}{2} |\nabla\phi|^2 - \frac{3GM_{\odot}}{2r} + \mathcal{Q} = 0$$

Where $\mathcal{Q} = -\frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{2} \frac{\nabla^2\sqrt{\Sigma}}{\Sigma}$ is the quantum pressure from \mathcal{P} .

Schrodinger-Like Equation with all of the Terms

Combine the equations for Ψ

$$i\hbar_{\odot}\partial_t\Psi = -\frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{2\Sigma_0}\nabla^2\Psi + \left(-\frac{3GM_{\odot}}{2r}\right)\Psi + Q\Psi$$

On the right, the first term is kinetic, the second term is gravitational plus centrifugal, and the third term is pressure. Thus we say for a protoplanetary disc we define:

$$\Psi(\vec{r}, t) = \sqrt{\Sigma(\vec{r}, t)}e^{i\phi(\vec{r}, t)}$$

$\Sigma(\vec{r}, t)$ is surface density of the disc (kg/m²)

$\phi(\vec{r}, t)$ is the velocity potential related to the gas flow velocity $\vec{v} = \nabla\phi$

This is the Madelung transformation, used to map fluid equations to a Schrodinger-like form.

Quantum mechanics: $|\psi|^2$ is the probability density which is dimensionless.

My Classical Theory: $|\Psi|^2 = \Sigma(\vec{r}, t)$ is the physical mass density (kg/m²).

Ψ describes a classical density wave in the disc, not a probability wave. So peaks in $|\Psi|^2$ correspond to regions of high gas/dust density (like where planets form).

Ramming It Through The Schrodinger Wave Equation To See What Not To Do

(This section in collaboration with Deep Seek) We want to model the Solar System as an analog to modeling an electron around a proton in a hydrogen atom, and do the most obvious thing, almost the default computation for such a scenario, which is to imagine a rotating protoplanetary disc with the Sun at the center and write the equation for the Schrödinger wave equation in cylindrical coordinates, then find the wave function for the Earth. To do this we would use the planet Mercury ($n=1$) orbit as the ground state. But, as we said, the wave function is a probability density and the Solar System is classically mechanical having many differences from the atom, like planets don't jump between orbits, electrons do. But we want to ram it through the equation because to look at what is wrong you can see why something else that works, is right. We do that now. The general time-independent Schrodinger equation is;

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi + V\psi = E\psi$$

The Laplacian in cylindrical coordinates is:

$$\nabla^2 = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \right) + \frac{1}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2}$$

The Schrodinger equation in cylindrical coordinates is:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left[\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \rho} \right) + \frac{1}{\rho^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \phi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial z^2} \right] + V(\rho, z)\psi = E\psi$$

To solve this equation for the solar system we consider it formed from a rotating disc of gas and dust called the protoplanetary disc, For V , the gravitational potential we have

$$mV_{grav} = - \frac{GM_{\odot}}{\sqrt{\rho_z + z^2}}$$

For the centripetal potential from the disc's rotation we have

$$mV_{cent} = - \frac{L^2}{2m\rho^2}$$

Where L is angular momentum. The wave function ψ describes the density distribution of the gas/dust in the disc. For a thin disc we have $z \rightarrow 0$ giving:

$$mV_{grav} = - \frac{GM_{\odot}m}{\rho}$$

Since the orbital velocity is $v_{\phi} = \sqrt{GM_{\odot}/\rho}$ and $L = m\rho v_{\phi} = m\sqrt{GM_{\odot}\rho}$. This gives

$$mV_{cent} = \frac{L^2}{2m\rho^2} = - \frac{GM_{\odot}m}{2\rho}. \text{ The total potential is:}$$

$$mV(\rho) = mV_{grav} + mV_{cent} = - \frac{GM_{\odot}m}{2\rho}$$

The time independent Schrodinger Equation in 3 dimensions in cylindrical coordinates is

$$-\frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{2M_e} \left[\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \rho} \right) + \frac{1}{\rho^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \phi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial z^2} \right] + -\frac{3GM_{\odot}M_e}{2\rho} \psi = E\psi$$

Where \hbar_{\odot} is the Solar System Planck constant and M_e is the mass of the Earth. If there is no azimuthal dependence and we neglect z-dependence because its second derivative is very small, we have

$$-\frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{2M_e} \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{d}{d\rho} \left(\rho \frac{d\psi}{d\rho} \right) - \frac{GM_{\odot}M_e}{2\rho} \psi = E\psi$$

The analog for the Bohr radius in the hydrogen atom, the orbital of an electron in its ground state for the Solar System is:

$$a_{\odot} = \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_{\odot}M_{mercury}^2}$$

Where we use the mass of the planet Mercury because it is the first planet, $n=1$, which would be the ground state. To get the Mercury orbit we need $\hbar_{\odot} = 9.1488E38J \cdot s$

$$a_{\odot} = \frac{(9.1488E38)^2}{(6.674E-11)(1.989E30kg)(3.3E23kg)^2} = 5.79E10m$$

Which is correct for the average orbital distance of Mercury. We introduce a dimensionless coordinate:

$$\xi = \frac{\rho}{a_{\odot}}$$

The energy scale is;

$$E_0 = -\frac{GM_{\odot}M_{mercury}}{a_{\odot}} = \frac{(6.674E-11)(1.989E30kg)(3.3E23kg)}{5.79E10m} = -7.5658E32J$$

The equation becomes

$$\frac{d^2\psi}{d\xi^2} + \frac{1}{\xi} \frac{d\psi}{d\xi} + \left(\frac{1}{\xi} + \epsilon \right) \psi = 0$$

Where $\epsilon = E/E_0$. Where E_0 would be the energy for the ground state. For bound states, which is for $\epsilon < 0$, this resembles the radial hydrogen equation for which the solution is a Laguerre Polynomial which is modulated by an exponential decay:

$$\psi_n(\xi) = \sqrt{\frac{(n-1)!}{2n(n!)^3}} \cdot \xi e^{-\xi/n} L_{n-1}^1 \left(\frac{2\xi}{n} \right)$$

with eigenvalues:

$$E_n = -\frac{E_0}{n^2} = -\frac{GM_{\odot}M_{mercury}}{2n^2 a_{\odot}}$$

L_{n-1}^1 are the associated Laguerre polynomials, for Earth orbit ($n=3$) this gives

$$\psi_3(\xi) \propto \xi e^{-\xi/3} \left(6 - \frac{4\xi}{3} + \frac{4\xi^2}{27} \right)$$

Earth's wave function ($n=3$) is then

$$\psi_3(\xi) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{729a_{\odot}^3}} \xi e^{-\xi/3} \left(6 - \frac{4\xi}{3} + \frac{4\xi^2}{27} \right)$$

The peak of $|\psi(\xi)|^2$ occurs at:

$$\xi_{peak} = n^2 \Rightarrow \rho_{peak} = n^2 a_{\odot}$$

Substituting $a_{\odot} = 5.79E10m$

$$\rho_{earth} = 5.21E11m \approx 3.5AU$$

This is just beyond the asteroid belt (near its outer edge). It may explain why there is so much debris there, it may have had a high probability of being there. In fact, in my theory, we will see my equations take an inverted form for their orbital number on the far side of the asteroid belt. I say this is because of the radiation pressure of the Sun blowing the lighter elements out beyond it cause gas giant to form there, and interior to the asteroid belt, the heavier elements stay in resulting in terrestrial planets. The asteroid belt is where material begins to break up, and what are gases but the atoms of solids broken up. So, at this point we realize we need to bring in the radiation pressure of the Sun into our wave equation to solve it properly. We add this in now. The radiative force of the Sun is:

$$F_{rad} = \frac{L_{\odot}\sigma}{4\pi c\rho^2}$$

Where L_{\odot} is the solar luminosity ($\sim 328E26W$), σ is the cross-sectional area of the particle (for simplicity one assumes spherical grains with $\sigma = \pi r^2$), c is the speed of light and ρ is the radial distance from the Sun. The potential energy is

$$V_{rad} = - \int F_{rad} d\rho = \frac{L_{\odot}\sigma}{4\pi c\rho}$$

We define a dimensionless parameter

$$\beta = \frac{F_{rad}}{F_{grav}} = \frac{L_{\odot}\sigma}{4\pi GM_{\odot}m}$$

The effective potential is:

$$V_{eff} = V_{grav} + V_{cent} + V_{rad} = \left(\beta - \frac{3}{2} \right) \frac{GM_{\odot}m}{\rho}$$

The Schrodinger equation becomes

$$-\frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{2M_e} \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{d}{d\rho} \left(\rho \frac{d\psi}{d\rho} \right) + \left(\beta - \frac{3}{2} \right) \frac{GM_{\odot}M_e}{\rho} \psi = E\psi$$

We form another dimensionless parameter

$$\gamma = \beta - \frac{3}{2}$$

$$-\frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{2M_e} \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{d}{d\rho} \left(\rho \frac{d\psi}{d\rho} \right) + \gamma \frac{GM_{\odot}M_e}{\rho} \psi = E\psi$$

We say will say the Bohr radius is

$$a_{\odot} = \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_{\odot}m^2 |\gamma|}$$

We have the dimensionless coordinate

$$\xi = \frac{\rho}{a_{\odot}}$$

And dimensionless energy

$$\epsilon = E/E_0$$

$$E_0 = \frac{GM_{\odot}m}{2a_{\odot} |\gamma|}$$

Substituting these we have

$$\frac{d^2\psi}{d\xi^2} + \frac{1}{\xi} \frac{d\psi}{d\xi} + \left(\frac{2}{\xi} + \epsilon \right) \psi = 0$$

This is the same as hydrogen's radial equation but with rescaled charge but the same asymptotic behavior. The general solution for bound states is:

$$\psi_n(\xi) \propto \xi^l e^{-\xi/n} L_{n-l-1}^{2l+1} \left(\frac{2\xi}{n} \right)$$

Where

n is the principle quantum number, l is angular momentum quantum number which is zero for simplicity since we ignore ϕ -dependence, and L is the associated Laguerre polynomials. For $l=0$, the ground state ($n=1$) is:

$$\psi(\xi) \propto e^{-\xi}$$

The first excited state at $n=2$ orbital is

$$\psi_2(\psi) \propto \left(1 - \frac{\xi}{2} \right) e^{-\xi/2}$$

And, the second excited state is $n=3$ orbital (Earth) is:

$$\psi_3(\xi) \propto \left(1 - \frac{2\xi}{3z} + \frac{2\xi^2}{27}\right) e^{-\xi/3}$$

The peak is where the probability density $|\psi_n(\xi)|^2 = 0$. For $n=3$ we have

$$|\psi_3(\xi)|^2 \propto \left(6 - \frac{4\xi}{3} + \frac{4\xi^2}{27}\right) e^{-2\xi/3}$$

The peak occurs at $\xi_{peak} \approx n^2 = 9 \Rightarrow \rho_{peak} = 9a_{\odot}$ but a_{\odot} depends on γ . That is,

$$a_{\odot} = \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_{\odot}m^2 |\gamma|}$$

We see if $\beta - \frac{3}{2}$ and β are small which corresponds to weak radiation pressure, the $\gamma \approx -1.5$, and a_{\odot} is similar to the value I have for Mercury orbit as the ground state. But, if β increases, $|\gamma|$ shrinks, and a_{\odot} blows up, pushing the peak even farther out. So, radiation pressure destabilizes the orbit, the potential becomes non-binding meaning there are no stable orbits. For beta less than 15 the peak is at still less than the 3.5 AU, not at Earth's 1 AU. The Quantum numbers don't match observed orbits because Mercury at $n=1$ is forced to a_{\odot} but Earth ends-up outside the asteroid belt. The n^2 scaling is too steep for planetary orbits, whereas in my theory they are proportional to n . But, the final wave equation is:

$$|\psi_3(\xi)|^2 \propto \left(6 - \frac{4\rho}{3a_{\odot}} + \frac{4\rho^2}{27a_{\odot}^2}\right) e^{-\rho/3a_{\odot}}$$

We see it is not so absurd to treat the Earth quantum mechanically, that the wave equation doesn't position the Earth so far from the Sun that it is 4 lights away at the closest star Alpha Centauri, but rather is within the Solar System around the asteroid belt, as well as for the first planet Mercury, which has the probability of being around the Earth's position. But, we find ultimately my solutions in my theory put the right where it should be by treating the wave function as not a probability density but as classical field for the protoplanetary disc when formed as a Lagrangian for the principle of least action.

Theory For Inertia

I had two equations that gave the radius of a proton with characteristic times of one second each. I had to break down the equations in terms of their operational parameters as described by a geometric model. This is what I came up with, a proton is a 4d hypersphere who's cross-section is a sphere. Of course occupying the dimension of time (4th dimension in drawing) is the vertical component of the drawing. I have to draw this 3d cross-section as a circle (we cannot mentally visualize four dimensions). The proton is moving through time at the speed of light (vertical component in the drawing) it is a bubble in space. The normal force holding it in 3d space $F_n = h/(ct_1^2)$ is proportional to the inertia created by the pliability of space measured by G. So when we push on it (Force applied in drawing) there is a counter force explaining Newton's action/reaction.

I think you could look at this another way: the cross sectional area of the proton moving against space is in the opposite direction of the force applied and h is the granularity of space, G still its pliability. That is to say, the flux of a normal force to a hemisphere is over the area of the cross-section of the sphere.

It is the goal of this opening section to provide a theory for inertia, that quality of a mass to resist change in motion. We want the the theory to include not just the quantum mechanics constant for energy over time h Planck's constant, but to include the universal constant of gravitation G , the constant c the speed of light from relativity, and α the fine structure constant for theories of electric fields so as to bring together the things that have been pitted against one another: quantum mechanics, relativity, classical physics, electric fields, and gravitational fields. Towards these ends we will suggest a proton is a 3D cross-section of a 4D hypersphere held in place countering its motion through time by a normal force that produces its inertia (measured in mass in kilograms) much the same way we model a block on an inclined plain countered by friction from the normal force to its motion. The following is the illustration of such a proton as a cross-sectional bubble in space:

To get the ball rolling, I had found a wave solution to the Earth/Moon/Sun system where the Earth orbiting the Sun is like an electron orbiting a proton with a quantum mechanical solution. I found this solution had a characteristic time of one second. But, I found as well, I could describe the proton as

having a characteristic time of one second, and that this yielded the radius of a proton very close to that obtained by modern experiments. So, it is now before me to come up with a theory for the proton in terms of these characteristic times before I present my theory for a wave solution of the Solar System.

The expressions for the characteristic times of 1-second for the proton that I found, were:

$$1. \quad \left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} \right) \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} = 1 \text{ second}$$

$$2. \quad \left(\sqrt{\phi \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = 1 \text{ second}$$

Where $\phi = 0.618$ is the golden ratio, r_p is the radius of a proton, and m_p is the mass of a proton. We find these produce close to the most recent measurements of the radius of a proton, if you equate the left sides of each, to one another:

$$3. \quad r_p = \phi \frac{h}{c m_p}$$

$$4. \quad r_p = 0.816632E - 15m$$

To derive this equation for the radius of a proton from first principles I had set out to do it with the Planck energy, $E = hf$, given by frequency of a particle, and from mass-energy equivalence, $E = mc^2$:

$$E = hf$$

We take the rest energy of the mass of a proton m_p :

$$E = m_p c^2$$

The frequency of a proton is

$$f_p = \frac{m_p c^2}{h}$$

We see at this point we have to set the expression equal to ϕ . So we need to come up with a theory for inertia that explains it:

$$\frac{m_p c^2}{h} \cdot \frac{r_p}{c} = \phi = \frac{m_p c}{h} r_p$$

$$m_p r_p = \phi \cdot \frac{h}{c}$$

The radius of a proton is then

$$r_p = \phi \cdot \frac{h}{cm_p}$$

In order to prove our theory for the radius of a proton as incorporating ϕ , we will apply our model outlined involving a normal force, F_n to a 3d cross-section of a 4d hypersphere countering its direction through time, t . We begin by writing equation 1 as:

$$5. \quad m_p = \frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} \cdot \frac{r_p}{1second}$$

Where G , the constant of gravitation measures the pliability of space, and h the granularity of space, and c the speed of propagation. m_p measures the inertia endowed in a proton. We write equation 2 as:

$$6. \quad 1 = \frac{\phi}{9} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3} \cdot \frac{h}{c(1second)^2} \cdot \frac{h}{c}$$

We now say that $t_1 = 1second$ and that the normal force is

$$7. \quad F_n = \frac{h}{ct_1^2}$$

This gives us:

$$8. \quad 1 = \frac{\phi}{9} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} \cdot F_n$$

$$= \frac{\pi}{9\alpha^4} \cdot \frac{F_n}{G} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p^2} \left(\phi \frac{h}{cm_p} \right)$$

Since $r_p = \phi \frac{h}{cm_p}$, we have

$$9. \quad 1 = \frac{\pi}{9\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{F_n}{G} \cdot \frac{r_p^2}{m_p^2}$$

This gives

$$10. \quad m_p = \frac{1}{3\alpha^2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\pi r_p^2 F_n}{G}}$$

πr_p^2 is the cross-sectional area of the proton countering the normal force, F_n , against its motion through time, this is measured by G the constant of gravitation. It is to say that

$$11. \quad m_p \propto \sqrt{\frac{\text{AreaCrossSectionProton} \cdot F_n}{G}}$$

And, the coupling constant is

$$12. \quad C = \frac{1}{3\alpha^2}$$

Let us see if this is accurate:

$$F_n = \frac{h}{ct_1^2} = \frac{6.62607E - 34 J \cdot s}{(299,792,458 m/s)(1s^2)} = 2.21022E - 42 N$$

$$m_p = \frac{18769}{3} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\pi(2.21022E - 42 N)}{6.674E - 11 N \frac{m^2}{kg^2}}} (0.833E - 15 m) = 1.68E - 27 kg$$

We used the experimental value of a proton $r_p = 0.833E - 15 m$. And we have demonstrated that our model of a proton as a 3D cross-section of a 4D hypersphere countering the normal force against its motion through time gives its inertia that can counter a force at right angles to its motion through time and the normal force.

It is thought that the proton does not have an exact radius, but that it is a fuzzy cloud of subatomic particles. As such depending on what is going on can determine its state, or effective radius. It could be that the proton radius is as large as

$$r_p = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{cm_p}$$

$$r_p = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{6.62607E - 34}{(299,792,458)(1.67262E - 27)} = 0.88094E - 15 m$$

Which it was nearly measured to be before 2010 in two separate experiments. Or as small as

$$r_p = \phi \cdot \frac{h}{cm_p} = 0.816632E - 15 m$$

Which is closer to current measurements, which have decreased by 4% since 2010, and could get smaller. In which case the characteristic time, t_1 , could be as large as

$$\left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = 1.03351 \text{seconds}$$

Using $2/3$ as a fibonacci approximation to ϕ . Or, it could be as small as

$$\left(\sqrt{\phi \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = \sqrt{(0.618) \frac{(352275361)\pi(0.833E - 15m)}{(6.674E - 11)(1.67262E - 27kg)^3}} \cdot \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{6.62607E - 34}{299792458}$$

=0.995 seconds

Or perhaps more often it is in the area of:

$$\frac{1}{6\alpha^2 m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h 4\pi r_p^2}{G c}} = 1.004996352 \text{seconds}$$

But, what this tells us is that the unit of a second might be a natural constant. And, since the second comes from dividing the Earth rotation period into 24 hours, and each hour into 60 minutes, and each minute into 60 seconds, which ultimately comes to us from the ancient Sumerians who first settled down from hunting, wandering, and gathering and flaking stones into spearpoints to invent agriculture, writing, and mathematics, that this might be related to the mechanics of our Solar System. We find if we take the second as natural we have a wave mechanics solution to our Solar System with a characteristic time of one second that is connected to the characteristic time of the proton, thus connecting macro scales (the solar system) to micro scales (the atom). We will formulate such a theory now...

Theory Outline: I have found some equations that fit together very accurately and nicely in the context of a quantum mechanical approach to structuring solutions of Nature, that indeed satisfy such a theoretical context in a complete sense. The result has solutions at the core of cosmology (the origin and fate of the universe), star systems mechanics, astrobiology (the study of the habitability of star systems in general), particle physics (like the atom's proton), theories showing a common structure between the macrocosmos and microcosmos, biology, formation of planetary systems from the protoplanetary disc, archaeology, archaeoastronomy (the study of ancient megalithic (stone) observatories), and SETI (The Search For Extraterrestrial Intelligence). It is the purpose of this section to outline some the key concepts concisely, and succinctly in the theory.

To begin with, I developed a theory which has a wave solution to the Earth/Moon/Sun system much like the quantum mechanical solution for the atom. Interestingly, the characteristic time that describes this system is neatly one second to two places after the decimal. The ground state I found is given by our Moon orbiting the Earth, and is

$$1. \quad \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{1}{c} = 1second$$

M_m is the mass of the Moon. I find \hbar_{\odot} , which is my Planck-type constant for the Solar System, much like the Planck constant in quantum mechanics used to describe the atom \hbar , in our theory is given by one second as well, and not just by that, but by the kinetic energy of the our home planet, the Earth, the planet in our Solar System optimized for the conditions for life. I find

$$2. \quad \hbar_{\odot} = (1second)KE_e$$

where KE_e is the orbital kinetic energy of the Earth. I know this value for \hbar_{\odot} is accurate because the solution for the energy of the Earth orbiting around the Sun using this value, which is much like the solution for an electron around a proton in an atom, is 99.5% accurate. It is:

$$3. \quad KE_e = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

where $n = 3$ is the earth orbital number, and R_{\odot} is the radius of the Sun, and R_m is the radius of the Moon, M_e is the mass of the Earth, M_m is the mass of the Moon, and G is the universal constant of gravitation. The radius of the Sun, R_{\odot} , plays the role of Z , the number of protons being orbited by an electron in an atom, but must be normalized by the radius of the Moon, R_m . This gives it a size of 400 because $R_{\odot}/R_m = 400$. So we see the Moon plays an important and central role in the quantum solution of our solar system, not just in the this equation, but in the ground state equation. It plays such a central role, that I have suggested the condition for optimal habitability of a planet in the habitable zone is given by the conditions of a perfect eclipse of the star by its moon as seen from the habitable planet, which is exactly what we have with our Earth/Moon/Sun system. That condition is:

$$4. \quad \frac{r_{planet}}{r_{moon}} = \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}}$$

Where r_{planet} is the orbital radius of the habitable planet (like the Earth), r_{moon} is the orbital radius of the moon, like the orbital radius of our moon around the Earth, R_{star} is the radius of the star, like our Sun, and

R_{moon} is the radius of the moon, like the Earth's moon. I use this in my theory to solve star systems in general—not just our Solar System— for optimal habitability, because we know our Moon orbiting the Earth holds the Earth at its tilt to its orbit around the Sun making it optimally habitable because this prevents temperature extremes and allows for the seasons. Here is where my theory has taken a very nice turn. The Earth as it rotates, determining the length of its day, loses energy to the Moon, meaning its rotation is slowing down, but very slowly only noticeably over geologic time, meaning the day length is lengthening ever so slowly over vast epochs, and that a very long time ago was a little shorter than it is today. However, to establish the optimal day length, we want it to be what it is today, about 24 hours, and in order to establish that, the Earth day of 24 hours should produce a characteristic time of one second. I had found it did close to this in the kinetic energies of the Moon and the Earth in their orbits. I had found that

$$5. \quad \frac{KE_m}{KE_e}(EarthDay) = 1.1 - 1.3seconds$$

There is a range in the answer because the Moon's orbit is not perfectly circular, though close to it, as well as that of the Earth. However I wanted this value to be closer to a second. I recently found that it is because of the obvious adjustment I had failed to make but should have, and that is we must include the effects of the Earth's tilt to its orbit, which is 23.5 degrees, so we must include the cosine of this angle to put the equation in the components of the Earth's spin in its orbital plane around the Sun. So, we have now our equation for a 24 hour day can indeed be considered a second in that we now have

$$6. \quad \frac{KE_m}{KE_e}(EarthDay)\cos(\theta) = 1.0seconds$$

But not only are we offering a wave solution for the Solar System like we have with the atoms, but it turns out we are offering the rudiments of a theory of particle physics, and not just that, a relationship between the microcosmos, the atom's protons, and the macrocosmos; planetary systems. I say this because I found that the same characteristic time of the Earth/Moon/Sun system is characteristic of the proton and predicts very accurately modern measurements of the radius of the proton. I found

$$7. \quad \left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} \right) \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} = 1second$$

$$8. \quad \left(\sqrt{\phi \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = 1second$$

r_p is the proton radius, r_m its mass. $\phi = 0.618$ is the golden ratio. α the fine structure constant. Since the left sides of these equation are both equal to a second, they are equal to one another. When we set them equal to one another, we find they very accurately yield the observed radius of the proton in the most recent experiments. We find the radius of a proton is given by

$$9. \quad r_p = \phi \frac{h}{c m_p}$$

But this characteristic time of one second is not just in the Solar System, and atom's proton, but in the basis of life chemistry, carbon, and the hydrocarbons, the skeletons of life chemistry. I found

$$10. \quad \frac{1}{6\text{protons}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 1\text{second is carbon (C)}$$

$$11. \quad \frac{1}{1\text{proton}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 6\text{seconds is hydrogen (H)}$$

Which is to say that six protons, which is carbon, the basis of life as we know it, has a characteristic time of one second because in the first equation above, we have a mass divided by the mass of a proton, times seconds, giving six protons times a second (6 proton-seconds) which means 6 protons (carbon, the basis of life) has a characteristic time of one second. This means that 1 proton, hydrogen, has a characteristic time of six seconds. Hydrogen is the most fundamental element in the periodic table of the elements which was theoretically created in the so-called *big bang* that gave birth to the universe, and is the element from which all of the other heavier elements were made by stars. This six-fold symmetry that is in hydrocarbons, the skeletons of biological chemistry, is fundamental to defining the periodic table of the elements because it has been found that the six protons of carbon and their respective charges, interact with its six electrons, their respective charges, to balance to make carbon the most stable element mathematically in which to describe the rest of the atoms in the periodic table. This is no doubt related to the regular hexagon, a six-sided polygon which tessellates (tiles a surface without leaving gaps) because it has its radii equal in length to its sides. This hexagonal tessellating property is used by bees to make their honeycombs. So we see our theory now goes beyond the atom and the solar system. That it goes to biological chemistry. But, it does not stop there. It seems to go into cosmology, the study of the origin and fate of the universe. We see this because my equations link proton properties to 1-second, and protons were fixed in the universe at 1 second after it, meaning we could be seeing a universal clock that has influenced everything since the Big Bang.

The idea is that neutrino decoupling (neutrinos stop interacting with one another) happens when the reaction rate of weak interactions Γ falls below the Hubble parameter, the expansion rate of the universe H . The reaction rate per particles is given by

$$\Gamma \approx G_F^2 T^5$$

G_F is the Fermi constant is about $1.166E - 5 GeV^{-2}$, and T is the temperature of the Universe. The expansion rate of the universe is given by

$$H \approx \frac{T^2}{M_{Pl}}$$

Where M_{Pl} is the Plank mass is about $1.22E19 GeV$. Γ and H have units of inverse time (s^{-1}). Neutrino decoupling happens when

$$G_F^2 T^5 = \frac{T^2}{M_{Pl}}$$

This is when the number of protons in the universe was set in place which, as it would turn out, is close to one second in rough estimate.

The expansion rate of the Universe is governed by the Friedmann equation

$$H^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3}\rho$$

Where ρ is the energy density of the Universe. It is

$$\rho \propto T^4$$

The Hubble expansion rate is

$$H \propto \frac{T^2}{M_{Pl}}$$

$$M_{Pl} \approx 2.4E18GeV$$

Since

$$t \propto \frac{1}{H}$$

we have

$$t \propto \frac{M_{Pl}}{T^2}$$

We said protons and neutrons are set in the universe when it has cooled in its expansion to about 1MeV.

We have

$$t \propto \frac{2.4E18GeV}{(1E-3GeV)^2} = 2.4E24GeV^{-1}$$

This was done in Planck units where time can be expressed in inverse energy. Since in Planck units

$$1GeV^{-1} = 5.39E-25s$$

we have

$$t \approx (2.4E24)(5.39E-25)$$

$$t \approx 1.3seconds$$

This theory seems, then, to have applications at the core of cosmology, astrobiology (the study of life in the universe in general), solar system mechanics, particle physics, theories of common structure between micro-scales and macro-scales, and biology . But, as we will see now, has applications at the core of star system formations from protoplanetary discs, and in archaeology and archaeoastronomy (the study of

ancient stone observatories, for example). We see this because I have found that the pressure gradient of the protoplanetary disc, as a function of radius, that gave birth to our solar system, is given by:

$$12. \quad P(R) = P_0 \left(\frac{R}{R_0} \right)^{-\frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}}}$$

$$13. \quad \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} 24 = 60$$

$$14. \quad L_{earth} = \frac{4}{5} \pi M_e f_e R_e^2$$

Where the rotational angular momentum, L_{earth} , is given by the mass of the Earth, the size of the Earth, and its rotation frequency. The value is 2.5, which is 60/24, by modeling our solar system is found in the theory of solar system formation to be the exponent in the pressure gradient for the protoplanetary disc from which our solar system formed. This is the solution to:

$$15. \quad \frac{dP}{dr} = -\rho \left(\frac{GM_{\star}}{r^2} - \frac{v_{\phi}^2}{r} \right)$$

The protoplanetary disc that evolves into the planets has two forces that balance its pressure, the centripetal force of the gas disc due to its rotation around the protostar v_{ϕ}^2/r and the inward gravitational force on the disc from the protostar GM_{\star}/r^2 , and these are related by ρ the density of the gas that makes up the disc.

I can use this to solve not just star systems in general, but to provide a theory for optimally habitable star systems.

In order to apply this to other star systems, we have to be able to predict the radius of the habitable planet, presumably in the n=3 orbit. I found the answer to be in the Vedic literature of India. They noticed that the diameter of the Sun is about 108 times the diameter of the Earth and that the average distance from the Sun to the Earth is about 108 solar diameters, with 108 being a significant number in Yoga. So I wrote the equivalent:

$$16. \quad R_{planet} = 2 \frac{R_{\star}^2}{r_{planet}}$$

The surprising result I found was, after applying it to the stars of many spectral types, with their different radii and luminosities (the luminosities determine r_{planet} , the distances to the habitable zones), that the radius of the planet always came out about the same, about the radius of the Earth. This may suggest optimally habitable planets are not just a function of the distance from the star, which determines their temperature, but are functions of their size and mass probably because they are good for life chemistry atmospheric composition, and gravity. Here are just a few examples using the data for several spectral types:

...

F8V Star

Mass: 1.18

Radius: 1.221

Luminosity: 1.95

$$M_{\star} = 1.18(1.9891E30kg) = 2.347E30kg$$

$$R_{\star} = 1.221(6.9634E8m) = 8.5023E8m$$

$$r_p = \sqrt{1.95L_{\odot}AU} = 1.3964AU(1.496E11m/AU) = 2.08905E11m$$

$$R_p = \frac{2R_{\star}^2}{r_p} = 2 \frac{(8.5023E8m)^2}{2.08905E11m} = \frac{6.92076E6m}{6.378E6m} = 1.0851EarthRadii$$

F9V Star

Mass: 1.13

Radius: 1.167

Luminosity: 1.66

$$M_{\star} = 1.13(1.9891E30kg) = 2.247683E30kg$$

$$R_{\star} = 1.167(6.9634E8m) = 8.1262878E8m$$

$$r_p = \sqrt{1.66L_{\odot}AU} = 1.28841AU(1.496E11m/AU) = 1.92746E11m$$

$$R_p = \frac{2R_{\star}^2}{r_p} = 2 \frac{(8.1262878E8m)^2}{1.92746E11m} = \frac{6.852184E6m}{6.378E6m} = 1.0743468EarthRadii$$

G0V Star

Mass: 1.06

Radius: 1.100

Luminosity: 1.35

$$M_{\star} = 1.06(1.9891E30kg) = 2.108446E30kg$$

$$R_{\star} = 1.100(6.9634E8m) = 7.65974E8m$$

$$r_p = \sqrt{1.35L_{\odot}AU} = 1.161895AU(1.496E11m/AU) = 1.7382E11m$$

$$R_p = \frac{2R_{\star}^2}{r_p} = 2 \frac{(7.65974E8m)^2}{1.7382E11m} = \frac{6.751E6m}{6.378E6m} = 1.05848EarthRadii$$

G1V Star

Mass: 1.03

Radius: 1.060

Luminosity: 1.20

$$M_{\star} = 1.03(1.9891E30kg) = 2.11E30kg$$

$$R_{\star} = 1.060(6.9634E8m) = 7.381E8m$$

$$r_p = \sqrt{1.20L_{\odot}AU} = 1.0954AU(1.496E11m/AU) = 1.63878589E11m$$

$$R_p = \frac{2R_{\star}^2}{r_p} = 2 \frac{(7.381E8m)^2}{1.63878589E11m} = \frac{6.6491E6m}{6.378E6m} = 1.0425EarthRadii$$

As you can see we consistently get about 1 Earth radius for the radius of every planet in the habitable zone of each type of star. It might be that radius is right for life in terms of gravity and densities for the elements. I got these results for the stars from spectral types F5V to K3V. It probably goes beyond that.

In order to get r_{planet} , the distance of the habitable planet from the star, we use the inverse square law for luminosity of the star. If the Earth is in the habitable zone, and if the star is one hundred times brighter than the Sun, then by the inverse square law the distance to the habitable zone of the planet is 10 times that of what the Earth is from the Sun. Thus we have in astronomical units the habitable zone of a star is given by:

$$17. \quad r_{planet} = \sqrt{\frac{L_{\star}}{L_{\odot}}} AU$$

We see our theory has applications to archaeology because the second came to us historically from the ancient Sumerians because they divided the Earth day (rotation period) into 24 hours, and, because each hour and minute got further divisions by 60 because their base 60 counting system was inherited by the ancient Babylonians who were the ultimate source of dividing the hour into minutes and the minutes into seconds. I have found this system is given by the rotational angular momentum of the Earth in terms the solar system Planck-type constant, because, as I already pointed out:

$$18. \quad \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} 24 = 60$$

$$19. \quad L_{earth} = \frac{4}{5} \pi M_e f_e R_e^2$$

This base 60 counting combined with dividing the day into 24 units is mathematically optimal because the rotational angular momentum incorporates not just the day (rotation period of the Earth) but the mass and size of the Earth. And, as I said, we are touching on archaeoastronomy, as well. This is because $60/24=2.5$ and the Scottish engineer, Alexander Thom, found ancient megalithic (stone) observatories throughout Europe may have been based on a unit of length he called the megalithic yard and that the separations between stones, that align with celestial positions and cycles, are recurrently separated by 2.5 megalithic yards. Like in Stonehenge.

Finally, this has applications in SETI (The Search For Extraterrestrial Intelligence) because we have found that the unit of one second may be a universal constant, and, as such, alien civilizations might use it. As such in sending us a radio message to let us know that they are there may be encoded, for example, or pulsed, in intervals of a second, aside from the fact that the theory has to do with habitable star systems in general, perhaps giving us an idea of what to look for in finding them, and in understanding them.

I have computed my Planck-type constant, \hbar_{\odot} , as such:

$$\hbar_{\odot} = (hC)KE_e$$

$$hC = 1second$$

Where

$$C = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2 c} \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{G m_p^3}}$$

$$20. \quad \hbar_{\odot} = (hC)KE_{earth} = (1.03351s)(2.7396E33J) = 2.8314E33J \cdot s$$

Conclusion: We live in a mysterious and enigmatic universe where a great deal defies explanation. Through the characteristic time of one second we may be able to describe a great deal of it in a unified perspective that has applications across various disciplines from the physical to the biological and the astrobiological. Here, we have laid out the basis set for a complete theory, in simple terms, but a great deal remains to be done in opening it up with more sophisticated mathematics and computer modeling than I have been able to do. We need to do this with various specializations in many fields that no one person can understand in their entirety.

The Solar Solution Our solution of the wave equation for the planets gives the kinetic energy of the Earth from the mass of the Moon orbiting the Earth, but you could formulate based on the Earth orbiting the Sun. In our lunar formulation we had:

$$1. \quad KE_e = \sqrt{3} \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2 \hbar_\odot^2}$$

We remember the Moon perfectly eclipses the Sun which is to say

$$2. \quad \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} = \frac{r_e}{r_m}$$

Thus equation 1 becomes

$$3. \quad KE_e = \sqrt{3} \frac{r_e}{r_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2 \hbar_\odot^2}$$

The kinetic energy of the Earth is

$$4. \quad KE_e = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{GM_\odot M_e}{r_e}$$

Putting this in equation 3 gives the mass of the Sun:

$$5. \quad M_\odot = \sqrt{3} r_e^2 \cdot \frac{GM_e}{r_m} \cdot \frac{M_m^3}{\hbar_\odot^2}$$

We recognize that the orbital velocity of the Moon is

$$6. \quad v_m^2 = \frac{GM_e}{r_m}$$

So equation 5 becomes

$$7. \quad M_\odot = \sqrt{3} r_e^2 \cdot v_m^2 \cdot \frac{M_m^3}{\hbar_\odot^2}$$

This gives the mass of the Moon is

$$8. \quad M_m^3 = \frac{M_\odot \hbar_\odot^2}{\sqrt{3} r_e^2 v_m^2}$$

Putting this in equation 1 yields

$$9. \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_\odot}{2 r_e^2 v_m^2}$$

We now multiply through by M_e^2/M_e^2 and we have

$$10. \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2r_e^2 v_m^2 M_e^2}$$

The Planck constant for the Sun, \hbar_\odot , we will call L_p , the subscript p for Planck. We have

$$L_p = r_e v_m M_e = r_e v_m M_e = (1.496E11m)(1022m/s)(5.972E24kg) = 9.13E38kg \cdot \frac{m^2}{s}$$

$$L_p^2 = r_e^2 v_m^2 M_e^2 = 7.4483E77J \cdot m^2 \cdot kg = 8.3367E77kg^2 \cdot \frac{m^4}{s^2}$$

We write for the solution of the Earth/Sun system:

$$11. \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2L_p^2}$$

We can write 11 as

$$12. \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

Where we say

$$\hbar_\odot = 9.13E38J \cdot s$$

$$h_\odot = 2\pi\hbar_\odot = 5.7365E39J \cdot s$$

Let us see how accurate our equation is:

$$\begin{aligned} KE_e &= \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2L_p^2} \\ &= \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \frac{(6.67408E-11)^2 (5.972E24kg)^4 (1.9891E30kg)}{2(8.3367E77kg^2 \cdot \frac{m^4}{s^2})} \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} (6.759E30J)$$

$$\frac{R_\odot}{R_m} = \frac{6.957E8m}{1737400m} = 400.426$$

$$KE_e = 2.70655E33J$$

We have that the kinetic energy of the Earth is

$$KE_{earth} = \frac{1}{2}(5.972E24kg)(30,290m/s)^2 = 2.7396E33J$$

Our equation has an accuracy of

$$\frac{2.70655E33J}{2.7396E33J} = 98.79\%$$

Which is very good.

Let us equate the lunar and solar formulations:

$$KE_e = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

$$KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

$$\sqrt{3} \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_\odot^2} = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2L_p^2}$$

This gives:

$$13. \quad L_p = \sqrt{\frac{M_e^2 M_\odot}{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}} \cdot \hbar_\odot$$

We remember that

$$\hbar_\odot = (hC)KE_e$$

$$hC = 1second$$

$$\text{And since, } KE_e = \frac{1}{2} M_e v_e^2$$

$$14. \quad 2v_m = \frac{v_e^2}{r_e} (1second) \sqrt{\frac{M_e^2 M_\odot}{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}}$$

$$\sqrt{\frac{M_e^2 M_\odot}{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}} = \sqrt{\frac{(5.972E24kg)^2 (1.9891E30kg)}{(7.34763E22kg)^3 (1.732)}} = 321,331.459 \approx 321,331$$

Equation 14 becomes

$$15. \quad 1second = 2r_e \frac{v_m}{v_e^2} \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_e^2 M_\odot}}$$

The condition of a perfect eclipse gives us another expression for the base unit of a second. L_p is another version of the Planck Constant, which is intrinsic to the the solar formulation as opposed to the lunar formulation.

Jupiter and Saturn We want to find what the wave equation solutions are for Jupiter and Saturn because they significantly carry the majority of the mass of the solar system and thus should embody most clearly the dynamics of the wave solution to the Solar System. We also show here how well the solution for the Earth works, which is 99.5% accuracy.

I find that as we cross the asteroid belt leaving behind the terrestrial planets, which are solid, and go to the gas giants and ice giants, the atomic number is no longer squared and the square root of the the orbital number moves from the numerator to the denominator. I believe this is because the solar system here should be modeled in two parts, just as it is in theories of solar system formation because there is a force other than just gravity of the Sun at work, which is the radiation pressure of the Sun, which is what separates it into two parts, the terrestrial planets on this side of the asteroid belt and the gas giants on the other side of the asteroid belt. The effect the radiation pressure has is to blow the lighter elements out beyond the asteroid belt when the solar system forms, which are gases such as hydrogen and helium, while the heavier elements are too heavy to be blown out from the inside of the asteroid belt, allowing for the formation of the terrestrial planets Venus, Earth, and Mars. The result is that our equation has the atomic number of the heavier metals such as calcium for the Earth, while the equation for the gas giants has the atomic numbers of the gasses. We write for these planets

$$E = \frac{Z}{\sqrt{n}} \frac{G^2 M^2 m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

So, for Jupiter we have (And again using the maximum orbital velocity which is at perihelion):

$$KE_j = \frac{1}{2} (1.89813E27kg)(13720m/s)^2 = 1.7865E35J$$

$$E = \frac{Z_H}{\sqrt{5}} \frac{(6.67408E-11)^2 (1.89813E27kg)^2 (7.347673E22kg)^3}{2(2.8314E33)^2}$$

$$E = \frac{Z_H}{\sqrt{5}} (3.971E35J) = Z_H (1.776E35J)$$

$$Z_H = \frac{1.7865E35J}{1.776E35J} = 1.006 \text{ protons} \approx 1.0 \text{ protons} = \text{hydrogen}(H)$$

Jupiter is mostly composed of hydrogen gas, and secondly helium gas, so it is appropriate that $Z = Z_H$.

Our equation for Jupiter is

$$E_j = \frac{Z_H}{\sqrt{5}} \frac{G^2 M_j^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

Where Z_H is the atomic number of hydrogen which is 1 proton, and $\sqrt{n} = \sqrt{5}$ for the orbital number of Jupiter, $n = 5$. Now we move on to Saturn...

$$KE_s = \frac{1}{2} (5.683E26kg)(10140m/s)^2 = 2.92E34J$$

$$E = \frac{Z}{\sqrt{6}} \frac{(6.67408E - 11)^2 (5.683E 26k g)^2 (7.347673E 22)^3}{2(2.8314E 33)^2}$$

$$= \frac{Z}{2.45} (3.5588E 34J) = Z(1.45259E 34J)$$

$$Z(1.45259E 34J) = (2.92E 34J)$$

$$Z = 2\text{protons} = \text{Helium}(He)$$

The equation for Saturn is then

$$E_6 = \frac{Z_{He}}{\sqrt{6}} \frac{G^2 M_s^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

It is nice that that Saturn would use Helium in the equation because Saturn is the next planet after Jupiter and Jupiter uses hydrogen, and helium is the next element after hydrogen. As well, just like Jupiter, Saturn is primarily composed of hydrogen and helium gas.

The accuracy for Earth orbit is

$$E_n = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

$$\frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} = \frac{6.96E 8m}{1737400m} = 400.5986$$

$$E_3 = (1.732)(400.5986) \frac{(6.67408E - 11)^2 (5.972E 24k g)^2 (7.347673E 22k g)^3}{2(2.8314E 33)^2} =$$

$$= 2.727E 33J$$

The kinetic energy of the Earth is

$$KE_e = \frac{1}{2} (5.972E 24k g) (30,290m /s)^2 = 2.7396E 33J$$

$$\frac{2.727E 33J}{2.7396E 33J} 100 = 99.5 \%$$

Which is very good, about 100% accuracy for all practical purposes. The elemental expression of the solution for the Earth would be

$$E_3 = \sqrt{3} \frac{Z_{Ca}^2 G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

Where

$$\frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \rightarrow Z^2$$

In this case the element associated with the Earth is calcium which is $Z=20$ protons.

Modeling Star Systems With The Theory The best way to solve star systems with our theory would be to use

$$1.0 \quad \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{1}{c} = 1second, \quad 3.0 \quad L_{earth} = \frac{4}{5}\pi M_e f_e R_e^2$$

$$2.0. \quad P(R) = P_0 \left(\frac{R}{R_0} \right)^{\frac{-L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}}}, \quad 4.0. \quad \hbar_{\odot} = t_c K E_e$$

Where here $t_c = 1second$. Equation 2.0 becomes

$$5.0. \quad \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} = p$$

Where for Earth $p=2.5$, the exponent in the pressure gradient for its protoplanetary disc. From this we get \hbar_{\odot} . We now get the characteristic time, t_c , from

$$\hbar_{\odot} = t_c K E_e$$

by using

$$6.0. \quad v_e = \sqrt{\frac{GM_e}{r_e}} \quad \text{and} \quad 7.0. \quad K E_{earth} = \frac{1}{2} M_e v_e^2$$

And we have t_c . We can now put t_c in equation 1.0

$$\frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{1}{c} = 1second$$

Which here is 1 second for the Earth, to get the mass of the moon, M_m . But to use equation 5, we need L_{earth} from equation 3.0. This requires the mass of the Earth, the frequency of the earth, which we get from the planet's day (Its rotation rate) and the radius of the planet. We have all of these values for habitable planets in a K2V star and an M2V star, but they are tidally locked. We have the frequencies because the planets are tidally locked, so their planets rotation periods are equal to their orbital periods. If we can't measure the planet's radius in another star system, we might obtain it from:

$$8.0. \quad R_e = \frac{2R_{\odot}^2}{r_e}$$

Which works for the Earth. We can get the orbital radius of our Moon from

$$9.0. \quad r_m = R_{\odot} \frac{Ag}{Au} = \frac{R_{\star}}{(1.8)}$$

It is given by the ratio of silver (Ag) to gold (Au) by molar mass is equal to r_m/R_{\odot} . The radius of the planet's moon we suggested is given by a perfect eclipse:

$$10.0. \quad \frac{R_{\star}}{R_m} = \frac{r_p}{r_m}$$

We have already applied our theory to the Earth/Moon/Sun System and it worked out nicely. Now we want to apply this ideal approach we just outlined, to it, so we can test it. We start with the angular momentum of the Earth. It is given by

$$L_{earth} = \frac{4}{5} \pi M_e f_e R_e^2 \quad \text{Or, ...}$$

$$L_e = \frac{4}{5} \pi (5.972E24kg) \frac{1}{(86400seconds)} (6.378E6m)^2$$

$$= 7.07866672E33J \cdot s$$

The orbital velocities and kinetic energies of the Earth are given by:

$$v_p = \sqrt{\frac{GM_{\star}}{r_p}} = \sqrt{\frac{(6.674E-11)(1.989E30kg)}{(1.496E11m)}} = 29,788.24m/s$$

$$KE_p = \frac{1}{2} M_p v_p^2 = \frac{1}{2} (5.972E24kg)(29,788.24m/s)^2 = 2.65E33J$$

We can now determine \hbar_{\star} :

$$\hbar_{\star} = \frac{L_p}{p} = \frac{(7.07866672E33J \cdot s)}{2.5} = 2.831467E33J \cdot s$$

This is correct for our solar system's Planck constant. We have the characteristic time is

$$t_c = \frac{\hbar_{\star}}{KE_p} = \frac{(2.831467E33J \cdot s)}{2.65E33J} = 1.068seconds \approx 1second$$

Which is correct as well. Now we compute the mass of our moon...

$$M_m^3 = \frac{(2.831467E33J \cdot s)^2}{(6.674E-11)(299,729,458m/s)(1.068seconds)}$$

$$M_m = 7.213E22kg$$

This is also very accurate (actual value: 7.347673kg). Now we compute the orbital radius of the Moon...

$$r_m = R_{\star} \frac{A_g}{A_u} = R_{\star} / (1.8) = \frac{6.957E8m}{1.8} = 3.865EE8m$$

This is accurate too (actual value: 3.84E8m). From this we have the radius of the Moon:

$$R_m = R_\star \frac{r_m}{r_p} = (6.957E8m) \frac{3.865E8m}{1.496E11m} = 1.79738E6m$$

This is pretty accurate, too. The actual value is 1.7374E6m

Now to get the density of the Moon...

$$V_m = \frac{4}{3}\pi R_m^3 = \frac{4}{3}\pi(1.79738E6m)^3 = 2.432E19m^3$$

$$\rho_m = \frac{7.213E22kg}{2.432E19m^3} = 2.96587g/cm^3 \approx 3g/cm^3$$

This is good, our Moon is about 3.344g/cm³. Now we want to check

$$1second = 2r_e \frac{v_m}{v_e^2} \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_e^2 M_\odot}}$$

$$v_m = \sqrt{\frac{GM_p}{r_m}} = \sqrt{\frac{(6.674E-11)(5.972E24kg)}{(3.865E8m)}} = 1,015.5m/s$$

$$2(1.496E11m) \frac{1,015.5m/s}{(29,788.24m/s)^2} \sqrt{\frac{(7.213E22kg)^3(1.732)}{(5.972E24kg)^2(1.989E30kg)}} = 1.03648sec \approx 1second$$

So this gives the correct characteristic time for the Earth/Moon/Sun system. Let's compute the planet day characteristic time...

$$1second \approx \frac{KE_m}{KE_e} (EarthDay)$$

$$KE_m = \frac{1}{2}(7.213E22kg)(1,015.5m/s)^2 = 3.719E28J$$

$$\frac{KE_m}{KE_e} (PlanetDay) = \frac{(3.719E28J)}{(2.65E33J)} (86,400sec) = 1.2seconds$$

We see the system for modeling star systems works.

We can make a program to model star systems in general given the spectral class of the Star. So HR diagrams plot mass versus luminosity to give spectral types of stars. So F Stars would be more luminous blue stars, G stars would be yellow medium luminosity stars, and K stars would be less luminous orange stars, and so on. There are ten divisions of each, and a "V" meaning "five" indicates the star is on the main sequence. So our Sun is a G2V star. A medium luminosity, yellow star. Here is a my program in C that does that for the method we just outlined.

```

//
// main.c
// modelsystem
//
// Created by Ian Beardsley on 2/9/25.
//

#include <stdio.h>
#include <math.h>

int main(int argc, const char * argv[]) {
    float R_p, M_p, R_s, M_s, t_c, M_m, rho_m, rho_p, PlanetDay,
    V_p, StarRadius, PlanetRadius, PlanetMass, StarLuminosity, PlanetOrbit,
    StarMass, r_p, T_p, p, L_p, KE_p, v_p, T_m, Tmoon, C_m;
    float G=6.674E-11, hbarstar, PDCT, Tsquared, T, PlanetYear;
    float r_m, R_m, V_m, MoonDensity, part1, part2, part3, v_m, KE_m;
    int i;
    printf ("What is the radius of the star in solar radii? ");
    scanf ("%f", &StarRadius);
    printf ("What is the mass of the star in solar masses? ");
    scanf ("%f", &StarMass);
    printf ("What is the luminosity of the star in solar luminosities? ");
    scanf ("%f", &StarLuminosity);

    PlanetOrbit=sqrt(StarLuminosity);
    r_p=PlanetOrbit*1.496E11;
    M_s=1.9891E30*StarMass;
    Tsquared=((4*3.14159*3.14159)/(G*M_s))*r_p*r_p*r_p;
    T=sqrt(Tsquared);
    PlanetYear=T/31557600;

    printf("Do you want us to compute the planet radius, 1=yes, 0=no? ");
    scanf("%i", &i);
    R_s=6.9364E8*StarRadius;
    if (i==1)
    {
        R_s=6.9364E8*StarRadius;
        R_p=2*(R_s*R_s)/r_p;
        PlanetRadius=R_p/6.378E6;
    }
    else
    {
        printf("What is the planet radius in Earth radii?: ");
        scanf("%f", &PlanetRadius);

        R_p=PlanetRadius*6.378E6;
    }

    printf("What is the mass of the planet in Earth masses? ");
    scanf("%f", &PlanetMass);

    M_p=PlanetMass*5.972E24;

    printf ("What is the planet day in Earth days? ");
    scanf ("%f", &PlanetDay);
    T_p=PlanetDay*86400;

```

```

printf("That is %f seconds \n", T_p);
{
    printf("What is p the pressure gradient exponent of the
protoplanetary disc? ");
    scanf("%f", &p);

    M_s=1.9891E30*StarMass;
    r_m=R_s/1.8;

    v_p=sqrt(G*M_s/r_p);
    L_p=0.8*3.14159*M_p*(1/T_p)*R_p*R_p;

    KE_p=0.5*M_p*v_p*v_p;
    hbarstar=L_p/p;
    t_c=hbarstar/KE_p;

    part1=cbrt(hbarstar/(t_c));
    part2=cbrt(1/G);
    part3=cbrt(hbarstar/299792458);
    M_m=part1*part2*part3;

    R_s=StarRadius*6.9634E8;
    R_m=R_s*r_m/r_p;
    V_m=1.33333*3.14159*R_m*R_m*R_m;
    rho_m=(M_m/V_m);
    MoonDensity=rho_m*0.001;
    V_p=1.33333*3.14159*R_p*R_p*R_p;
    rho_p=(M_p/V_p)*0.001;

    printf("\n");
    printf("\n");

    printf("Angular Momentum of Planet: %f E33 \n", L_p/
1E33);

    printf("\n");
    printf("\n");

    printf("PlanetYear: %f years \n", PlanetYear);
    printf("PlanetYear: %f seconds \n", T);
    printf("planet orbital velocity: %f m/s \n", v_p);
    printf("planet mass: %f E24 kg \n", M_p/1E24);
    printf("planet mass: %f Earth masses \n", M_p/5.972E24);
    printf("planet radius %f meters \n", R_p);
    printf("planet radius: %f Earth Radii \n", PlanetRadius);
    printf("planet orbital radius: %f E11 m \n", r_p/1E11);
    printf ("planet orbital radius: %f Earth distances \n",
r_p/1.496E11);

    printf("planet KE: %f E33 J \n",KE_p/1E33);
    printf("planet density: %f g/cm3 \n", rho_p);
    printf("\n");
    printf("\n");
    printf("hbarstar: %f E33 Js \n", hbarstar/1E33);
    printf("characteristic time: %f seconds\n", t_c);
    printf("\n");
    printf("\n");

```

```

printf("Orbital Radius of Moon: %f E8 m \n", r_m/1E8);
printf("Orbital Radius of Moon: %f Moon Distances \n",
r_m/3.84E8);
printf("Radius of Moon: %f E6 m \n", R_m/1E6);
printf("Radius of Moon: %f Moon Radii \n", R_m/1.7374E6);
printf("Mass of Moon: %f E22 kg \n", M_m/1E22);
printf("Mass of Moon %f Moon Masses \n", M_m/
7.347673E22);
printf("density of moon: %f g/cm3 \n", MoonDensity);
printf("\n");
printf("\n");
v_m=sqrt(G*M_p/r_m);
KE_m=0.5*M_m*v_m*v_m;
PDCT=(KE_m/KE_p)*(T_p);
printf("Orbital Velocity of Moon: %f m/s \n", v_m);
printf("PlanetDay Characteristic Time: %f seconds \n",
PDCT);
C_m=2*3.14159*r_m;
T_m=C_m/v_m;
Tmoon=T_m*(1.0/24)*(1.0/60)*(1.0/60);
printf("Lunar Orbital Period: %f seconds \n", T_m);
printf("Lunar Orbital Period: %f days \n", Tmoon);

return 0;}}

```

Now we show running the program (3 examples) for a wide spread of spectral types including F, G, and K-type stars. We will need to input in the program not just the mass of the star, its luminosity, and size, but the pressure gradient exponent for the disc from which the star's planets formed.

To compute the moon's orbital radius I just use

$$r_m = R_{\odot} \frac{A_g}{A_u} = \frac{R_{\star}}{1.8}$$

Where A_g is the molar mass of silver and A_u is the molar mass of silver, a connection to the 1.8 that appears in our Solar System. We use this because we know it works for our Solar System. I compute the radius of the planet using

$$R_e = \frac{2R_{\odot}^2}{r_e}$$

But, give the option of putting in your own radius. I have run the program for F5V stars, through GV stars, to K3V stars and I use this equation to compute the radii of the planets because, again, we know it works for our star system, and further we found given the way the radius of a star varies with with luminosity in the HR diagram, this equation always gives a planet around the size of the Earth. I feel this size is ideal for planets with sophisticated life because of the laws of chemistry determining a functional density for the planet having water and the right gravity. As such I always use the planet day as one Earth day, which again I feel is optimal for life in terms of climate. So these values all constant, we only vary star mass, size, and luminosity as they work on the HR diagram. I also vary the pressure gradient exponent now using the average theoretical values it has for each spectral class. The trend is that it steadily decreases on average with mass and luminosity of the star though it can go up and down depending on the peculiarities of the system. One of the reasons is that while for a G2V star it can range on average from $p = 1.7-2.1$, for our Sun, a G2V star, it is actually high, it is 2.5. However, here we will

model stars with everything constant, as we said, but the pressure gradient will gradually decrease with spectral class, and when we do a G2V star, we won't use the Sun's data, but the average value for G2V stars. We will do lot's of models, allowing no gaps in the data for a plot, so we can get a well defined curve. We will use the upper value for p in instances here. We will also use

$$\frac{KE_{moon}}{KE_{planet}}(PlanetDay)\cos(0^\circ) \approx 1second$$

Instead of

$$\frac{KE_m}{KE_e}(PlanetDay)\cos(23.5^\circ) = 1second$$

Thus taking the tilt of the planet to its orbital as $\theta = 0^\circ$ and not what it is in particular for the Earth $\theta = 23.5^\circ$, which may actually be optimal for the most habitable types of planets around stars like our Sun. The average pressure exponents by spectral class are given in the following table...

Exponents For Pressure Gradient

Spectral Type	Typical p Range	Average
F5V	2.0-2.4	2.2
F6V	2.0-2.4	2.2
F7V	1.9-2.3	2.1
F8V	1.9-2.3	2.1
F9V	1.8-2.2	2.0
G0V	1.8-2.2	2.0
G1V	1.8-2.2	2.0
G2V	1.7-2.1	1.9
G3V	1.7-2.1	1.9
G4V	1.6-2.0	1.8
G5V	1.6-2.0	1.8
G6V	1.5-2.0	1.75
G7V	1.5-1.9	1.7
G8V	1.4-1.8	1.6
G9V	1.4-1.8	1.6
K0V	1.3-1.7	1.5
K1V	1.3-1.7	1.5
K2V	1.2-1.6	1.4
K3V	1.1-1.5	1.3

Now we run the program using this for examples of three spectral types...

F5V Star

What is the radius of the star in solar radii? 1.473
 What is the mass of the star in solar masses? 1.33
 What is the luminosity of the star in solar luminosities? 3.63
 Do you want us to compute the planet radius, 1=yes, 0=no? 1
 What is the mass of the planet in Earth masses? 1
 What is the planet day in Earth days? 1
 That is 86400.000000 seconds
 What is p the pressure gradient exponent of the protoplanetary disc? 2.4

Angular Momentum of Planet: 9.321447 E33

PlanetYear: 2.280109 years
 PlanetYear: 71954776.000000 seconds
 planet orbital velocity: 24888.847656 m/s
 planet mass: 5.972000 E24 kg
 planet mass: 1.000000 Earth masses
 planet radius 7325190.000000 meters
 planet radius: 1.148509 Earth Radii
 planet orbital radius: 2.850263 E11 m
 planet orbital radius: 1.905256 Earth distances
 planet KE: 1.849692 E33 J
 planet density: 3.627237 g/cm3

hbarstar: 3.883936 E33 Js
 characteristic time: 2.099775 seconds

Orbital Radius of Moon: 5.676287 E8 m
 Orbital Radius of Moon: 1.478200 Moon Distances
 Radius of Moon: 2.042695 E6 m
 Radius of Moon: 1.175720 Moon Radii
 Mass of Moon: 7.107576 E22 kg
 Mass of Moon 0.967323 Moon Masses
 density of moon: 1.990782 g/cm3

Orbital Velocity of Moon: 837.955261 m/s
 PlanetDay Characteristic Time: 1.165595 seconds
 Lunar Orbital Period: 4256210.000000 seconds
 Lunar Orbital Period: 49.261688 days
 Program ended with exit code: 0

G3V Star

What is the radius of the star in solar radii? 1.002
 What is the mass of the star in solar masses? 0.99
 What is the luminosity of the star in solar luminosities? 0.98
 Do you want us to compute the planet radius, 1=yes, 0=no? 1
 What is the mass of the planet in Earth masses? 1
 What is the planet day in Earth days? 1
 That is 86400.000000 seconds
 What is p the pressure gradient exponent of the protoplanetary disc? 2.1

Angular Momentum of Planet: 7.393050 E33

PlanetYear: 0.989814 years
 PlanetYear: 31236148.000000 seconds
 planet orbital velocity: 29789.738281 m/s
 planet mass: 5.972000 E24 kg
 planet mass: 1.000000 Earth masses
 planet radius 6523625.500000 meters
 planet radius: 1.022833 Earth Radii
 planet orbital radius: 1.480965 E11 m
 planet orbital radius: 0.989950 Earth distances
 planet KE: 2.649862 E33 J
 planet density: 5.135297 g/cm3

hbarstar: 3.520500 E33 Js
 characteristic time: 1.328560 seconds

Orbital Radius of Moon: 3.861263 E8 m
 Orbital Radius of Moon: 1.005537 Moon Distances
 Radius of Moon: 1.819172 E6 m
 Radius of Moon: 1.047066 Moon Radii
 Mass of Moon: 7.754257 E22 kg
 Mass of Moon 1.055335 Moon Masses
 density of moon: 3.074905 g/cm3

Orbital Velocity of Moon: 1015.987427 m/s
 PlanetDay Characteristic Time: 1.304901 seconds
 Lunar Orbital Period: 2387924.250000 seconds
 Lunar Orbital Period: 27.638012 days
 Program ended with exit code: 0

K3V Star

What is the radius of the star in solar radii? 0.755
 What is the mass of the star in solar masses? 0.78
 What is the luminosity of the star in solar luminosities? 0.28
 Do you want us to compute the planet radius, 1=yes, 0=no? 1
 What is the mass of the planet in Earth masses? 1
 What is the planet day in Earth days? 1
 That is 86400.000000 seconds
 What is p the pressure gradient exponent of the protoplanetary disc? 1.5

Angular Momentum of Planet: 8.340819 E33

PlanetYear: 0.435785 years
 PlanetYear: 13752343.000000 seconds
 planet orbital velocity: 36167.078125 m/s
 planet mass: 5.972000 E24 kg
 planet mass: 1.000000 Earth masses
 planet radius 6929175.500000 meters
 planet radius: 1.086418 Earth Radii
 planet orbital radius: 0.791609 E11 m
 planet orbital radius: 0.529150 Earth distances
 planet KE: 3.905860 E33 J
 planet density: 4.285367 g/cm3

hbarstar: 5.560546 E33 Js
 characteristic time: 1.423642 seconds

Orbital Radius of Moon: 2.909435 E8 m
 Orbital Radius of Moon: 0.757665 Moon Distances
 Radius of Moon: 1.932263 E6 m
 Radius of Moon: 1.112158 Moon Radii
 Mass of Moon: 10.277222 E22 kg
 Mass of Moon 1.398704 Moon Masses
 density of moon: 3.400867 g/cm3

Orbital Velocity of Moon: 1170.438843 m/s
 PlanetDay Characteristic Time: 1.557185 seconds
 Lunar Orbital Period: 1561850.125000 seconds
 Lunar Orbital Period: 18.076969 days
 Program ended with exit code: 0

Here is a plot of these results from F5V Stars to K3V stars:

Characteristic Time Vs. Planet Day Characteristic Time

Spectral Class	Characteristic Time (seconds)	Planet Day Characteristic Time (Seconds)
F5V	2.099775	1.165595
F6V	1.880435	1.182626
F7V	1.913523	1.215200
F8V	1.590791	1.202798
F9V	1.570746	1.237699
G0V	1.465727	1.266400
G1V	1.379592	1.275032
G2V	1.341468	1.300484
G3V	1.328560	1.304901
G4V	1.392148	1.325893
G5V	1.336611	1.324104
G6V	1.275932	1.320330
G7V	1.29042	1.351277
G8V	1.356775	1.379084
G9V	1.195302	1.387337
K0V	1.167964	1.412571
K1V	1.169154	1.424915
K2V	1.277586	1.492071
K3V	1.423642	1.557185

We see the characteristic time decreases as a curve to intersect close to a characteristic time of one second with a planet day characteristic time of one second as a straight line at a G3V star, a G5V star, and a G8V, which is a region near where our Sun is and may have something to do with it being so optimal for life. We note here that this uses the average value for a G2V star, and our Sun comes closer to a second because its pressure exponent is higher than on average, it is very high, or steep ($p=2.5$) which means the pressure of its disc drops rapidly with distance.

Planet Day Characteristic Time: $1second \sim \frac{KE_m}{KE_e}(EarthDay)$

Characteristic time: $\hbar_{\odot} = (1second)KE_e, \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{1}{c} = 1second$

Here we fit the curves for characteristic time and planet day characteristic time. We name the spectral types with number for input according to the following scheme.

F5V is 1.5, F6V is 1.6, F7V is 1.7,...G0V is 2.0, G1V is 2.1,...

For the characteristic time we fit the curve with a power law decay

$$y = 2.8x^{-\frac{3}{2}} + 1.1$$

For the planet day characteristic time we fit the curve with a straight line

$$y = 0.168x + 0.913595$$

Where we have chosen in $y = mx + b$,

$$m = \frac{G3V - F9V}{2.3 - 1.9} = 0.168$$

$$b = 1.165595 - 0.168(1.5)$$

We intend to fit the curves in the following plot:

The results are

Fitting The Characteristic Time For Spectral Class

Spectra Class=x	Characteristic Time (seconds)	$y=2.8x^{(-3x/2)+1.1}$	Spectra Class
1.5	2.099	2.2245	F5V
1.6	1.880435	2.0063	F6V
1.7	1.913523	1.8236	F7V
1.8	1.590791	1.6723	F8V
1.9	1.570746	1.54948	F9V
2.0	1.465727	1.45	G0V
2.1	1.379592	1.3705	G1V
2.2	1.341468	1.30757	G2V
2.3	1.328560	1.2582	G3V

Fitting Planet Day Characteristic Time

Spectral Class=x	Planet Day Characteristic Time (seconds)	$y=0.168x+0.913595$	Spectral Class
1.5	1.165595	1.165595	F5V
1.6	1.182626	1.182626	F6V
1.7	1.215200	1.199195	F7V
1.8	1.215200	1.215995	F8V
1.9	1.237699	1.232795	F9V
2.0	1.266400	1.249595	G0V
2.1	1.275032	1.266395	G1V
2.2	1.300484	1.283195	G2V
2.3	1.3049	1.29995	G3V

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